

TOWARDS POLYMERIC FIBERS' OPTIMIZATION AS REFRACTORY CASTABLE DRYING AGENTS - INSIGHTS FROM DIRECT VISUALIZATION

Murilo H. Moreira^{a*}, Alessandro Tengattini^{b,c}, Stefano Dal Pont^{b,c}, Victor C. Pandolfelli^a

^a Federal University of São Carlos, Graduate Program in Materials Science and Engineering, Rodovia Washington Luis, km 235 SP-310, 13565-905, São Carlos, São Paulo, Brazil.

^b CNRS, Grenoble INP, 3SR, Université Grenoble Alpes, 38000 Grenoble, France

^c Institut Laue-Langevin (ILL), 71 Avenue des Martyrs, 38000 Grenoble, France

*murilo.moreira@estudante.ufscar.br

ABSTRACT

Permeability-enhancing additives are often applied to mitigate the risk of explosive spalling during refractory castables drying. The reasoning is that the easier percolation of water within the material reduces the likelihood of water vapor pressurization, enabling faster drying, increased end-user productivity and a substantial CO₂ emissions reduction. Thanks to their advantageous features, polymer fibers are the predominant class of drying additives in the industry. The key challenge to unlocking optimized drying additives is understanding the detailed mechanisms of permeability enhancement provided by the polymeric fibers. Thus, neutron tomography was used to visualize the difference in the mass removal behavior of samples comprising polypropylene (PP), polyethylene (PE) and cellulose fibers. The PE and cellulose compositions initiated the drying process earlier, with the latter contributing to more extensive drying. Conversely, PP only accelerated the drying at later stages, however, it still achieved an efficiency comparable to cellulose.

INTRODUCTION

The removal of water from a partially or fully saturated porous material is defined as drying and it can occur through various mass transport mechanisms, such as molecular diffusion and capillary-driven flow [1]. These processes arise due to gradients in pressure, temperature and concentration, or a combination thereof [1]. The drying of refractory castables comprises the decomposition of the hydrated phases which is a thermally activated process in addition to the liquid water removal. This context and the requirement for short down times, the low intrinsic permeability of the castables, and their large structure dimensions, results in the use of heating for water removal at the required rates [1, 2].

Nevertheless, it still remains the most time-consuming step in the processing of refractory castables with hydraulic binders, directly influencing energy costs and production delays in high-temperature operations [3]. This is a consequence of the risk of facing explosive spalling, leading to an abrupt and catastrophic failure caused by pressurized vapor within the pores and thermomechanical stress [4]. Thus, slower heating rates and temperature plateaus, based on semi-empirical methods, are frequently adopted to ensure the safe drying of linings [1, 2]. High energy consumption is a direct consequence of these slower heating rates as demonstrated by Cunha et al. [5]. It was also shown that such procedures may even represent overly cautious approaches. By focusing on changes on the refractory composition instead of the boundary conditions, the use of polymeric fibers that enhance intrinsic permeability during heating is broadly employed to mitigate the explosive spalling risk [6].

In the review by Mohammed et al. [7], the state-of-the-art on adding polymeric fibers in the context of Portland cement concrete to increase its fire resistance was summarized highlighting that *the exact mechanisms* through which these additives enhance spalling resistance remain unclear. One of the hypothesis for the observed behavior of permeability increase are the one proposed by Zhang et al. [8] suggesting that the addition of polypropylene fibers induces microcracks due to differences in thermal expansion between the fibers and castable matrix. Another is the one by Innocentini et al. where it is proposed that the improvement stems from fiber melting and subsequent burning out [9]. This lack of knowledge prevents the optimization of the current fibers used and also limits the search for

better suitable alternatives, despite the ability to precisely engineer synthetic polymers for multiple requirements.

In-situ visualization techniques is a promising route to investigate the drying behavior of castables comprising polymeric fibers, as shown by the results of Stelzner et al. who studied the moisture transport in high-performance concrete (HPC) either with or without PP-fibers using X-ray-CT and ^1H NMR [11]. The results suggested that the samples with the permeability-enhancing additive exhibited a faster drying front. However, no comparison of different additives was made and permeability mechanisms were not fully explored, as well as intrinsic drawbacks of the methodology used related to the low interaction between water and X-rays. Using NMR, Barakat et al. showed that during the fiber melting in refractory castables containing PP, the drying front velocity was increased [12]. The water distribution was not identified and the use of different fibers was not studied either.

Therefore, the current work aims to apply neutron tomography for in-situ observations of the drying behavior of refractory compositions with different types of fibers. This technique was successfully used recently to prove that moisture accumulation occurs at the innermost positions of the sample (known as “moisture clog”) [13] and to study the effect of heating rate in such phenomenon [14]. This technique provides important information on the complex dynamics of the multiple mechanisms active during the castable drying.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

High-alumina castable compositions containing 5 wt.% calcium aluminate cement, with calcined, tabular and reactive aluminas were prepared. Polypropylene (PP), polyethylene (PE), or cellulose fibers were selected as drying additives and the compositions are detailed in Table 1. Adjustments in water content were required to achieve consistent flowability across samples with different fibers and the reference sample with no additive. Additionally, the fiber content varied by weight percentage to standardize the volumetric fraction of fibers across all additives tested.

Castable mixtures without fibers and those with PP and PE fibers, were prepared following the same method described in Moreira et al. [13]. Because the cellulose additive

needs to be swelled before promoting higher permeability during drying, half of the water content was pre-mixed with the fibers for five minutes in a bench mixer prior to castable preparation to ensure its hydration. Subsequently, this water-cellulose mixture was combined with the other components, following a protocol similar to that of the other compositions.

Table 1: Compositions of high alumina refractory castables considered in this work.

Raw Materials		5CAC (wt.%)	5CAC-PP (wt.%)	5CAC- PE (wt.%)	5CAC-Cel (wt.%)
Tabular Alumina, Almatis		74.0	74.0	74.0	74.0
Calcined and reactive alumina	CL370, Almatis	11.0	11.0	11.0	11.0
	CT3000SG, Almatis	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0
Calcium Aluminate Cement	Secar 71, Imerys	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
Drying Additive	PP, supplied by RHI-Magnesita	-	0.1	-	-
	PE, Emsil-Dry, Elkem	-	-	0.1	-
	Cellulose, Suzano	-	-	-	0.2
Distilled Water		4.5	4.7	4.6	5.4
Dispersant	Castement FS60, Basf	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2

The castables were poured into dense alumina cylindrical ceramic casings, measuring 3.6 cm in internal diameter and 5 cm in height, with open ends. The experimental setup for the in-situ drying tests is illustrated in Figure 1. An infrared heater was placed near the sample's top surface, and a heating rate of 20°C/min until reaching 600°C was applied, followed by a 30-minute plateau. A thermal insulator was used to fill the gap between the sample and the Teflon container, preventing lateral heating. As shown in Figure 1 b), the samples were positioned in the reverse orientation relative to their casting direction. The neutron beam was provided by the NeXT equipment from the Institut Laue-Langevin, France, providing the most intense cold neutron beam currently available in the world. The details on the imaging acquisition are present in [14].

Figure 1: (a) Experimental set up for the neutron tomography test at Institut Laue-Langevin (ILL) and (b) vertical slice of the neutron tomography highlighting the alumina casings.

The progression of the drying front was used to determine the sizes of the dried zones (DZ) and it was calculated with a gradient-based algorithm, as depicted in Figure 2. An alternative method for quantitatively evaluating water content evolution during drying involved calculating its normalized level intensity across sample slices. This was achieved by taking the ratio of the image intensity at a specific time point to the median intensity of the first 10 tomographies, which represents the initial state prior to drying.

Figure 2: Drying front position detection algorithm, i) the mean of the attenuation in the radial direction is calculated over the region of interest, ii) a Savitzky-Golay filter is applied and iii) the minimum of the derivative of the mean attenuation with respect to the height defines the drying front position (the blue vertical line).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

To facilitate the comparison across the tests, a relative time scale, t_r , was defined, where the initial time corresponds to the onset of the drying front progression, as determined by the methodology in Figure 2. The normalized attenuation for each sample in axial slices is presented in Figure 3. Composition 5CAC was the one with the slowest process and smaller drying zone (DZ, the blue area at the top). The mass transport behavior in the composition containing PP fibers showed faster drying between $t_r = 0$ min and $t_r = 12$ min, although the DZ size remained comparable to that of the 5CAC composition. By the end of the test, the DZ in the 5CAC-PP sample was approximately 1.5 times larger than in 5CAC.

The 5CAC-PE sample presented a moisture distribution at $t_r = 12$ min similar to the reference composition, indicating a permeability enhancement mechanism that is “activated” during heating. At the final stage, a larger DZ than the one in 5CAC was observed, suggesting an increased water removal rate over time, though the drying intensity was not as pronounced as in the other fiber-containing compositions. The 5CAC-Cel sample showed rapid and intense drying, with a constant water removal rate. At both $t_r = 12$ min and $t_r = 20$ min, 5CAC-Cel displayed the largest DZ and the lowest attenuation values.

Fig. 3: Normalized attenuation intensity at relative times, t_r , 0 min, 12 min and 20 min.

Figure 4 presents quantitative analyses considering the relative drying volume percentage. Composition 5CAC was the one where the water removal was the slowest, taking around 30 minutes to reach the 20% of relative drying volume. To reach similar drying

for the 5CAC-PP sample it took only 18 minutes, for 5CAC-PE 13 minutes and for the 5CAC-Cel 10 minutes. This is directly linked to the different mechanisms of actuation of the fibers.

Cellulose fibers are known to increase the permeability even at temperatures below 110°C [6], as water is released from the swollen fibers at relatively low temperatures, accelerating the drying process. In contrast, PP and PE fibers rely on thermally activated changes that occur at higher temperatures, resulting in an initial drying behavior similar to the 5CAC reference sample. However, as these fibers undergo phase transitions, permeability increases, speeding up the water removal.

Fig. 4: Relative drying volume versus the relative drying time. The dried volumes were obtained from the drying front position detection algorithm presented in Figure 2.

The effect of fibers on the moisture clog was evaluated by analyzing the evolution of the normalized average gray value within a disk of the sample, as depicted in Figure 5. 5CAC displayed the longest period of moisture accumulation, evidenced by gray values exceeding initial levels. Conversely for composition 5CAC-Cel a shorter moisture retention was seen, although the rate and intensity of moisture accumulation were slightly higher and occurred at a significantly faster rate. This suggests that moisture transport is enhanced in both directions, to the top and to the bottom of the sample. The increased permeability of the 5CAC-Cel composition speeds-up the water withdrawal, inducing a faster and safer drying process. A similar trend was observed for the PP and PE fiber-containing samples.

Therefore, in unidirectional drying, additives that “activate” at elevated temperatures may be less advantageous, as moisture accumulation can still occur in the cooler regions of the refractory castable, likely leading to explosive spalling.

Figure 5: Normalized averaged gray value evolution for the region of interest shown in the inset.

CONCLUSIONS

A significant benefit to reduce the carbon footprint associated with the use of hydraulic bonded castable refractories relies on a better understanding of the drying process which will enable the designing of optimized heating protocols. One valuable alternative to reducing the likelihood of facing explosive spalling during the water withdrawal from refractories is the use of polymeric fibers.

Therefore, this study explored the effects of various permeability-enhancing additives from a novel perspective by utilizing neutron tomography to observe, in real-time, the drying behavior of compositions containing polypropylene, polyethylene and cellulose fibers, in comparison to those without any additives. Results showed that the 5CAC composition presented the smallest dried zone, followed by 5CAC-PP and 5CAC-PE. The 5CAC-Cel sample showed the largest dried portion, indicating faster water removal with a consistent drying rate. The moisture clog observed with cellulose fibers was the largest, yet it had the shortest duration, whereas the additive-free sample showed a large moisture accumulation region, which could be linked to the explosive spalling phenomenon, due to a local reduction on the castable permeability.

Future studies will focus on improving the current methodology to directly investigate the thermal behavior of fibers, aiming to elucidate the mechanisms behind the increased

permeability in castables. A better understanding of these mechanisms could enable the design of more effective synthetic fibers or promote the use of alternative natural fibers that operate through similar processes as those seen in cellulose. This approach would further contribute to more sustainable practices, ensuring faster and safer drying.

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